

INCREASING THE EDUCATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES OF SOCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE PROCESS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. As we set ourselves the task of modernizing the country and democratizing society, forming a harmoniously developed generation, ensuring its spiritual security, we must find ways to focus not only on earning money, but also on spiritual education.

Keywords: modernization democratization of society, formation of a harmoniously developed generation, ensuring spiritual security, labor collectives, spiritual upbringing, labor collectives of social institutions,

Social institutions are a set of norms and rules that give stability to various forms of human activity. The process of their formation, that is, institutionalization, has led to the replacement of uncontrolled behavior with controlled behavior. It is known that this exchange had a great impact on the development of human society. In this sense, the emergence of social institutions can be considered a revolutionary phenomenon.

Of course, as human society developed, so did social reality. Human needs have changed radically, social relations have acquired a new character, it has become necessary to develop new norms and rules for the coordination of relations between people. Under the influence of these processes, the content, structure and functions of social institutions also improved. The social institutions that operate in any society today perform four main functions:

- coordination of activities and behavior of members of society in the field of

social relations;

- creating the necessary conditions to meet the needs and interests of all members of society;

- stabilization of social life, strengthening social partnership, solidarity between different classes and strata;

- to lay the foundation for the socialization of members of society.

- Social institutions - family, preschools, secondary schools, higher and secondary special education institutions, labor unions, public organizations act as a legacy that connects ancestors to generations, the past to the present, serves as a source of knowledge of the good qualities and qualities accumulated by ancestors , plays a decisive role in the development of man as an independent person.

It is known that the future of a society, a state, a person begins with the family. The family is the basic unit of society. The first notions and ideas about upbringing, homeland, people, independence and freedom, imprinted in the family, will be imprinted in the child's heart for a lifetime. "It is natural that the character of the child," the head of our state wrote, "is the spiritual criteria and views that determine the nature and worldview - the foundation of sacred concepts such as goodness and kindness, nobility and kindness, honor and dignity." [1]

However, this will require thinking about ways to solve some of the problems that exist in these social institutions.

First of all, the issue of raising the dignity of women in the family, raising the level of maternal education is still relevant.

Second, it also provided an opportunity to address the men's issue. Today, there is no organization, no newspaper, or magazine for men. The problem of men was overshadowed by the excessive glorification of women. That is why in all countries, men live 8-10 years less than women, and the process of their development as an independent person is protracted. This situation can eventually lead to a family far from material well-being, a child deprived of spiritual

upbringing. For this reason, Russian President Dmitry Medvedev stressed the need to develop the institution of paternity. [2]

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Third, the role of preschool institutions is also of particular importance. Its main task is to form the foundations of human perfection, to form the spiritual needs and basic skills.

Fourth, the educational work carried out in general education schools is a continuation of this purposeful, conscious activity within the framework of a single, holistic educational impact carried out by other social institutions of society. At the same time, the need to conduct work on a scientific basis to ensure the spiritual safety of young people in secondary schools has not been removed from the agenda. Only spiritual activities based on scientific achievements, not on nonsense, serve to highlight four main socio-psychological factors:

- Increased need for students to study universal and national values;
- to help to understand the socio-economic and spiritual problems;
- to study the cultural heritage of the past, which is an important source of formation of spiritual culture, the interaction of spiritual values with modern cultural life, to adhere to the advanced ideas put forward in practice, to ensure their longevity, to understand the need for development. [3]

-Fifth, higher and secondary special education institutions have a special place. Because it is in these places that the systematized spiritual views of young people are formed, their social qualities are decided, their life position is formed. Most importantly, higher and secondary special education institutions provide an opportunity to increase a person's mental capacity and intellectual potential. The mind, as Jalal al-Din Rumi put it, "is like a ruler in the human body. As long as the subjects of the body obey him, everything will go smoothly. If not, everything will be out of order." [4]

-Sixth, a central component of the system of social institutions is related to the work community. Because it is with the help of the labor collective that the individual begins to participate in social relations in society. As a result of socio-economic reforms in Uzbekistan, the image of the country's labor force has changed radically. Today, about 70 percent of labor communities belong to the private sector. This, of course, has a major impact on the educational capabilities of working communities. Such progress in science and technology, the rapid penetration of its achievements into the branches of the national economy led to the automation of production. In many scientific sources, the automation process is combined with the autonomy of production. Not really. Automation is the process of increasing the efficiency of the social production process, the introduction of technical means that allow the efficient use of various raw materials and materials. Any automation system includes two subsystems. One of them consists of technical units (machines), and the other is an operator (person). [5]

Unfortunately, this effect remains negative in most cases. This is because labor collectives engaged in the private sector are focusing on income. Issues related to spiritual education are not even planned. As a result, the educational potential of labor communities is not fully realized. As we set ourselves the task of modernizing the country and democratizing society, forming a harmoniously developed generation, ensuring its spiritual security, the focus of the working community is not only on earning money, but also on spiritual education. we need to find ways to deal with their problems.

It is obvious that there are many problems in the activities of social institutions that need to be addressed. Overcoming these problems will increase the role of social institutions in ensuring the spiritual security of the individual.

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